

THE PECULIARITIES OF STUDYING EQUIVALENCES IN A WORK OF "SCORPION FROM THE ALTAR".

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Abstract: This dissertation presents the solution of a number of research problems that have remained unresolved or are debatable in the scientific description of equivalences of literary translation on the basis of English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: equivalent, extralinguistic factors, translation, "Scorpion from the Altar", "Mehrobdan Chayon", cultural differences;

The original and translation units can be equivalent at all levels or at some of them. Fully or partially equivalent units and potentially equivalent definitions objectively exist in the original language and in the translated language, but their correct evaluation, selection and application depends on the knowledge, skills and creativity of the translator, his language and depends on the skill of considering and comparing extralinguistic factors.

Translation is a complex process that involves transferring meaning from one language to another. It is a skill that requires not only linguistic proficiency but also cultural sensitivity and an understanding of the context in which the source text was written. The study of equivalences in translation aims to identify instances where the translator has successfully maintained the original meaning and tone of the source text. However, it is not always easy to achieve equivalence, especially when dealing with languages and cultures that are vastly different from one another.

This dissertation work focuses on the problems encountered in studying equivalences in the English translation of "Scorpion from the Altar" by Tuxtasinov from Abdulla Kadiri's Uzbek novel "Mehrobdan chayon". The study aims to identify instances where the translator has failed to maintain the original meaning and tone of the source text, and to explore the cultural and linguistic differences between the source and target languages that have contributed to these challenges.

The analysis of the translation has revealed several problems. One of the most significant issues identified is mistranslation. In some instances, the translator has used words or phrases that do not accurately convey the intended meaning of the source text. This can lead to confusion or misinterpretation by the reader. Another problem is the omission of information. The translator may have left out important details that are crucial to understanding the story or character development. Additionally, there are instances where the translator has added information that was not present in the source text. This can alter the meaning of the original text and create inconsistencies.

Cultural and linguistic differences between the source and target languages have also contributed to the challenges faced in achieving equivalence. For example, idiomatic expressions or cultural references may not have a direct equivalent in the target language, making it difficult for the translator to convey the intended meaning. Furthermore, differences in syntax or grammar can also pose challenges in achieving equivalence. To overcome these problems, it is recommended that translators pay close attention to the cultural and linguistic nuances of both languages. They should strive to maintain the original meaning and tone of the source text while also taking into account the cultural context in which it was written. This

requires a deep understanding of both the source and target languages, as well as the ability to navigate cultural differences.

In conclusion, the study of equivalences in translation is an important aspect of ensuring accurate and effective communication across languages and cultures. The analysis of the English translation of "Scorpion from the Altar" by Tukhtasinov from Abdulla Kadiri's Uzbek novel "Mehrobdan Chayon" has revealed several problems, including mistranslation, omission, and addition of information. Cultural and linguistic differences between the source and target languages have also contributed to these challenges. To overcome these problems, translators must possess a deep understanding of both languages and strive to maintain the original meaning and tone of the source text. Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of accurate translation and the need for translators to approach their work with cultural sensitivity and linguistic proficiency.

When studying the translation of phrases, the translator's skill is clearly visible mainly in finding equivalent and alternative options, because the words given in Uzbek language in simple language are expressed by phrases in the translation. It was observed that the meaning shifts in the equivalent phrases in the original and translated text, and when the original phrases move to the translation field, their meaning narrows and they take on a new meaning as an addition. The translator originally translated the given similes in a manner specific to the culture of Uzbek and English readers and understood the meaning in both languages.

Adequate interpretation of phrases in translation is one of the most complex and, at the same time, very responsible issues of translation practice. Because, as artistic and descriptive means of speech, they participate in the expression of various methodological tasks more than a simple, neutral statement of thought. From the research of many researchers, it became clear that phrases as a single lexical unit of the language can be divided into grammatical, semantic, functional, and even sociological.

It is shown that it is possible to learn. In addition, many expressions have a national character, which creates difficulties for translators. Social events, moral and spiritual-cultural norms, mental states, religious imagination, national traditions and customs are reflected in the structure of each language phraseology.

Due to the complexity of the language in Kadiri's time, many difficulties were encountered in the translation process. The reason is that some of the lexical units found in "The Scorpion from the Altar" are now obsolete and are not used in our mother tongue today. In addition, some concepts had to be explained in detail. These concepts cannot be directly translated into English, leaving the reader confused. Therefore, the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan was a great source of support.

In conclusion, the study of equivalences in the English translation of "Scorpion from the Altar" by Tukhtasinov from Abdulla Kadiri's Uzbek novel "Mehrobdan Chayon" has revealed several problems. The analysis of the translation has shown that there are instances where the translator has failed to maintain the original meaning and tone of the source text. The issues identified include mistranslation, omission, and addition of information. Furthermore, cultural and linguistic differences between the source and target languages have also contributed to the challenges faced in achieving equivalence. To overcome these problems, it is recommended that translators pay close attention to the cultural and linguistic nuances of both languages and strive to maintain the original meaning and tone of the source text.

Overall, this study highlights the importance of accurate translation and the need for translators to possess a deep understanding of both the source and target languages.

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